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EMOTIONAL ECONOMY IN DIGITAL TRANSFORMATIONS OF MODERN SOCIETY

Hrushchinska Natalia, Mikhalchenko Oleksii. *«Emotional economy in digital transformations of modern society».* The article reveals the issues of emotional economy in the conditions of modern transformation processes taking into account the development of digital economy, emotional management, artificial intelligence. The processes of transformation of modern society are under the influence of the network economy as a catalyst for geoeconomic processes with an emphasis on broad informatization, globalization, and opens up great opportunities for humanity to expand the exchange of goods, services, information, technology and capital, humanitarian cooperation and spiritual enrichment. Such trends are receiving special attention in the context of global processes caused by quarantine measures for David-19. Today, the goal of digital technologies is to meet the needs of the population, which are changing with the development of IT developments, in particular - to create a more comfortable and efficient interaction between the public and the management system.

Keywords: emotional economy, transformation processes, digital economy.

Грущинська Наталія, Михальченко Олексій. *«Емоційна економіка в цифровій трансформації сучасного соціуму».* В статті розкриваються питання емоційної економіки в умовах сучасних трансформаційних процесах з урахуванням розвитку цифрової економіки, емоційного менеджменту, штучного інтелекту. Процеси трансформації сучасного соціуму відбуваються під впливом становлення мережевої економіки як каталізатора геоекономічних процесів з акцентом на широкій інформатизації глобалізація, та відкриває перед людством величезні можливості для розширення масштабів обміну товарами, послугами, інформацією, технологіями і капіталом, взаємодії в гуманітарній сфері та духовного збагачення особистості. Такі тенденції набувають особливої уваги в умовах світових процесів викликаних карантинними заходами щодо Covid-19. На сьогодні метою цифрових технологій є, задоволення потреб населення, які змінюються разом з розвитком ІТ-розробок, зокрема – створення більш комфортної й оперативної взаємодії громадськості та системи управління.

Ключові слова: емоційна економіка, трансформаційні процеси, цифрова економіка.

Грущинская Наталия, Михальченко Алексей. *«Эмоциональная экономика в цифровой трансформации современного социума».* В статье раскрываются вопросы эмоциональной экономики в условиях современных трансформационных процессах с учетом развития цифровой экономики, эмоционального менеджмента, искусственного интеллекта. Процессы трансформации современного социума происходят под влиянием становления сетевой экономики в качестве катализатора геоэкономических процессов с акцентом на широкой информатизации глобализация, и открывает перед человечеством огромные возможности для расширения масштабов обмена товарами, услугами, информацией, технологиями и капиталом, взаимодействия в гуманитарной сфере и духовного обогащения личности. Такие тенденции приобретают особое внимания в условиях мировых процессов вызванных карантинными мерами по Covid-19. На сегодня целью цифровых технологий является, удовлетворение потребностей населения, меняются вместе с развитием ИТ-разработок, в том числе - создание более комфортной и оперативного взаимодействия общественности и системы управления.

Ключевые слова: слова: эмоциональная экономика, трансформационные процессы, цифровая экономика.

Introduction. Elements of economic thinking of modern society are the ability to optimize labor activity, to have a constant desire to master and implement information technology tools, with efficient use of economic and natural resources. The specifics of economic thinking of an employee of a particular specialty and profession depends on the scope of his activities, position and other factors. In today's world of technoglobalization, emotional intelligence, emotional management, and the development of the subconscious become especially important. A quote from the Israeli historian Yuval Noah Harari, author of *Sapiens: A Brief History of Mankind* and *Homo Deus: A Brief History of Tomorrow*, underscores the urgency of these issues: "We may be one of the last generations of Homo sapiens. In a century or two, the Earth will be inhabited by organisms that will be as different from us as we are from Neanderthals or chimpanzees. Because in the next generations we will learn to modify our body and mind, and this will be the main product of the economy of the XXI century" [14].

The aim of the article is to try to reveal the features of emotional economy and emotional intelligence in the context of modern digital transformations with an emphasis on behavioral economics.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Issues of behavioral economics

are studied in the works of foreign and domestic authors such as D. Kanneman, A. Tversky, R. Schiller, D. Arieli, M. Alle, A. Suvorov, V. Belyanin. In general, the authors consider the application of behavioral economics in such areas as microeconomics, financial market, investment market. It is the shortcomings of the traditional economy that draw the attention of the founders of the behavioral economy (Behavioral Economics). The founders of this modern branch of the economy are considered to be American psychologists, namely the winner of the Nobel Prize in Economics in 2002 Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky. Their article "Prospect Theory: Decision Making Under Risk" was published in 1979 in the journal *Econometrica*. The paper emphasizes that people mostly show a tendency to completely irrational behavior. Through a series of scientific studies, they have concluded that the economy, in particular the market, is the result of human decisions. People's decisions are usually risky. In modern science, the ideas of behavioral economics are explored in the works of Dan Ariely, who found that irrational behavior is not chaotic. It is subject to certain models, so it is quite predictable, at least in statistical terms. According to V. Belyanin, behavioral economics is a branch of economic theory that takes into account the psychological characteristics of human perception, judgment and action in different

economic situations. However, there remains a significant list of issues that need analysis and in-depth research in the field of behavioral economics, namely methods that can calculate the share of psychological impact on the formation and implementation of any economic model, positive and negative effects of human behavior on economic efficiency. object of economics. Particular attention in the context of the study of emotional economics deserves issues of emotional intelligence, revealed in the works of D. Goleman, P. Salovey, J. Meyer, D. Caruso, R. Bar-On, S. Heine, R. Cooper, W. Dax, etc. Theoretical and methodological approaches to the problem of the relationship between intellectual and emotional were considered in the works of B.G. Ananiev, LS Vygotsky, SL Rubinstein, O.M. Leontiev, VM Мясищев, O.K. Tikhomirov and others. In particular, the outstanding psychologist LS Vygotsky singled out the problem of the unity of affect and intellect among the most important questions of psychology. The topic of research on the development of emotional intelligence is becoming relevant around the world, and in Ukraine is also gaining special approaches. Management systems are changing not only at the level of enterprises and organizations, but also approaches to assessing the public administration system. The concept of emotional intelligence is characterized by the ability of the individual to recognize and interpret emotions, as well as productively use them for optimal problem solving. Examining emotional intelligence, it should be noted that of particular interest is the intelligence of the leader as the ability to recognize and interpret emotions, use them to solve management problems. Increasing the level of emotional intelligence of the head of the enterprise improves the efficiency of each individual employee and the enterprise as a whole. The generally accepted notion of economics is determined by a set of social scientific disciplines on the economy, namely the organization and management of material production, efficient use of

resources, distribution, exchange, sale and consumption of goods and services.

The generally accepted notion of economics is determined by a set of social scientific disciplines on the economy, namely the organization and management of material production, efficient use of resources, distribution, exchange, sale and consumption of goods and services. However, a deeper consideration of economics should add a number of factors that affect statistical, econometric, mathematical data, namely factors whose research is focused on aspects of psychology, history, politics.

Presentation of the main material.

Technological development of post-industrial civilization, and partly the current stage is defined as post-industrial civilization, and involves the formation of VI-VII technological systems, based on the development of emotional intelligence, subconscious, biotechnology, technology related to morality and responsibility. A person's reaction to social processes: migration, rising prices, fluctuations in the dollar, etc. is a manifestation of emotions that can cause panic or calm the population, influencing further economic processes. The higher the economic consciousness of society, the more difficult it is exposed to possible influences, including manipulation. Especially given the basic psychological law formulated by the English economist J. Case, according to which people tend to increase income consumption, but not to the same extent as income increases. The economic consciousness of society must be realized by the national economic idea. The formation of the national economic idea depends on the choice of model of socio-economic development of the country. The economic consciousness of society is based on the presence of economic awareness of the population, its emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence (EQ) has several levels. The first is awareness of one's emotions; the second - the ability to manage their own emotions; third - awareness of other people's emotions; fourth - managing the emotions of others. In business, the ability to

manage the company's emotional resources is special, ie "emotional management". In today's world with active technological development, emotion control is a necessary component of a stable society. The cycle of changing types of economic sentiment, which in turn play an important role in changing cycles of business activity, is revealed in the scheme of SJ Lloyd, representative of the monetary school in political economy: , panic, stagnation, depression and calm again "[4]. What indicators can indicate the adequacy or emotional instability of the population? Let's try to assume that this is not just statistics of the mentally ill, but indicators of the effectiveness of social policy, namely the level and quality of life (a measure of material, spiritual and social needs of man, providing a set of material and social living conditions). Indicators are used to assess the living standards of the population: subsistence level; the value of the subsistence level; the value of the "consumer basket" of food; poverty line; minimum wage and minimum pension, etc. The following data can also testify to the state of emotional adequacy of society. Among people who can not control their emotions, natural mortality is 40% higher than in people who are emotionally stable, due to exacerbation of cardiovascular disease, diabetes, etc. [5]. In Ukraine, such negative trends are confirmed by high mortality rates, including due to the above diseases. According to the State Statistics Committee, the percentage of divorces in relation to registered marriages in the CIS countries, including Ukraine is about 60%, in most cases due to emotional problems. According to statistics, 90% of murders are committed in a state of affect, under the influence of alcohol and drugs. The world's statistics are 466078 murders per 100 thousand population, including the largest in Africa - 169,105 centuries., American countries are - 144648, Asian countries - 137120, European countries - 24025, including Ukraine, but , with one of the lowest results - 1551 murders. According to the WHO,

about 400 million people suffer from depression worldwide, in Ukraine such figures are more than 6% of the population. The number of suicides as a result of depression reaches up to three thousand people each year, and in Ukraine there are 20.1% of suicides per 100 thousand population. Statistical indicators of emotional intelligence of the population, which are interrelated with the economic assessment of the country, can be confirmed by the International Happiness Index [24].

Globalization opens up enormous opportunities for humanity to expand the exchange of goods, services, information, technology and capital, cooperation in the humanitarian sphere and the spiritual enrichment of the individual. At the same time, for a large part of the world, globalization poses significant threats, causing the division of countries into a "civilization center" and a "peripheral zone", deepening their differentiation in socio-economic and scientific and technological development.

Studying the processes taking place in the context of globalization, should take into account changes and globalization itself, its transformation, the catalysts of which include, above all, technological changes in society, leading to changes in economic, political, social, cultural spheres of life. The analysis of these areas can be considered effective and efficient in determining the research methodology.

If the XX century. was the era of industries based on the use of natural resources and efficient technologies, the XXI is dominated by "artificial intellectual industries", the economy of intellectual assets, the main factors of development of which are not production and implementation, but the idea, project, program. Globalization processes are characterized by a wide range of direct impact on the economy and its effectiveness. Large-scale social transformations are also related to global competition and competitiveness.

Technological development of the economy involves the development of the

economy through progressive changes, attracting investment, consistent growth of the scientific and technological sector, the knowledge economy. The lag in the development of the theory of technological systems, its non-use in the process of state forecasting and management lead to distortions in the development of the country. Technological systems are the leader of modern processes of post-industrial society.

The main problem of constructing the foundations of the new economic system in modern conditions is the factor of adaptation of its internal features to the national character of the industrial economy. New industries are specific elements of the national economy, as they are directly subject to the laws of global economic flows. Problems and prospects for their functioning - is a complex structural complex of the global and national economy. The main problem node of post-industrial design was the need to develop a model for the development of post-industrial humanitarian economy in a particular country.

In total, against the background of the rapid growth of the importance of the information component, the importance of industrial forms of economic organization is declining. The latest technologies provide a unique opportunity for countries with limited resources to "jump over" entire cycles of industrial development, which a few years ago had to go through to reach today's level of economic development of Western society.

The formation of post-industrial society involves a new historical phase of civilization, in which the main products of production are information and knowledge. Signs that distinguish the information society are: increasing the role of information and knowledge in society; increasing the share of information communications, products and services in gross domestic product; creating a global information space that provides effective information interaction of people, their access to global information resources and meet their needs for information products and services.

In modern society, information is becoming the most important value, and the industry of receiving, processing and transmitting information is a leading industry in which more and more significant capital is invested every year. According to leading scientists, information is becoming an important strategic resource, the lack of which leads to significant losses in the economy. Informatization of society is one of the decisive factors in modernizing the economy on market principles and the key to Ukraine's integration into the world community.

Attempts to measure information were first made in the early nineteenth century. However, the beginning of modern information theory was laid by the American cyberneticist K. Shannon in 1948, who defined information not as a social phenomenon, but in a technical aspect. After researching the characteristics and options for measuring information, philosophical scientific works on the qualitative nature of information begin to appear [20]. Thus, according to A. Ursul, information is part of such an attribute of materialism as reflection, which expresses diversity and can be objectified, transmitted and participate in all forms of movement in nature and society. In the 1980s, the number of philosophical publications on information decreased markedly, which can be explained by misconceptions about the development of the main theoretical principles of the problem. Simultaneously with the cessation of theoretical research of philosophers, information began to play an increasingly prominent role in socio-economic development and attract the attention of economists.

The main feature of the modern world is the use of artificial intelligence in almost every field of activity. Of course, the main world leaders in the artificial intelligence industry are the United States and China. According to financial indicators, the total volume of China's artificial intelligence technology industry by 2025 should reach \$ 60.3 billion, and by 2030 - to exceed \$ 150.8 billion. [21] In

general, the population of the world has a tendency to age, in particular, the population of China, in addition, the rapid decline of natural resources, the actualization of environmental problems. Much attention is increasingly being paid to the use of artificial intelligence, which should help create smart manufacturing, updated medicine, cities, agriculture and defense. In 2019, the G20 countries agreed on the principles of treatment of artificial intelligence, which provided the center for the use of artificial intelligence - man, and the basic legal principles, human rights and democratic values are aimed at supporting human values. By 2030, 400 to 800 million people worldwide are projected to lose their jobs through automation. A McKinsey & Company study found that about 30 percent of jobs in 60 percent of professions can be computerized, and 80 million jobs in the United States and 15 million in the United Kingdom. In 2013, a study by Oxford University academics entitled "The Future of Employment" was conducted, during which 702 common professions were studied. The study found that some professions, such as TV shopkeepers, tax clerks and referees, are at greater risk of extinction than others, such as recreational psychologists, dentists and doctors.

By 2020, the Fourth Industrial Revolution opened up the world of robotics and autonomous transport, artificial intelligence and machine learning, new materials, biotechnology and genomics. The strongest factors influencing the global economy are: the spread of the Internet, mobile communications, automation of routine intellectual work; cloud technologies and energy storage solutions; next generations of approaches to genome management; advanced robotics and driverless transport; 3D printing, etc. Accordingly, such processes will contribute to the destruction of professions that do not require high qualifications. Of course, among the negative consequences of the fourth industrial revolution are the following: the emergence of unemployment and the distribution of

world wealth - poor countries may still become poorer, but rich countries can expect significant shocks due to mass robotization of production; the flow of qualified personnel to rich countries, according to the possession of all new technologies. And the growing "significance" of the poor countries as raw materials and human resources for the rich; Rising cybersecurity threats - Many surveys around the world point to concerns about new threats of cyber attacks.

Conclusions. The analysis of the features of emotional economy and emotional intelligence in the conditions of modern digital transformations is carried out taking into account the processes taking place in the modern world space. The quarantine effects of COVID-19 have shown that digital skills that enable citizens to access information and services are crucial for the entire population. Harmonization of digital markets in Ukraine will lead to increased competition, which means improving online services at better prices and with more choice. This will attract investment, and stimulate trade and employment, contributing to the socio-economic development of countries. The EU's Digital Single Market is one of the European Commission's 10 policy priorities aimed at providing the best possible access to the online world for individuals and businesses. In order to bring the single market of the European Union into line with the digital age, it is necessary to remove unnecessary regulatory barriers and move from individual national markets to a single pan-European set of rules. Harmonization of digital markets is one of the key outcomes of EU policy to deliver tangible results to citizens in the Eastern Partnership. Regulatory tools, ways of implementation are through appropriate legislation and using financial, economic, administrative and political mechanisms of influence.

Digital markets, virtual economy, artificial intelligence require an appropriate response from the introduction of emotional intelligence as the ability of the individual to manage the emotional sphere on the basis of

intellectual analysis. The problem of emotional intelligence remains insufficiently studied both theoretically and experimentally, and requires a sound

scientific justification. The education system for the introduction of innovations and creative approaches is designed to find a balance between thinking and emotions.

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